

**NEW METAL COMPLEXES AND THEIR POSSIBLE APPLYING
BRANCHES IN AGRICULTURAL SECTOR BY QUANTUM CHEMICAL
ANALYSIS**

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Abstract. *In this article, the crystal arrangement of molecule for [Cu(PHBA)₂(MEA)₂] complex was analyzed. This analysis is necessary to determine what kind of supramolecular structures (2- or 3-dimensional framework) are formed as a result of intermolecular interactions, because it depends on the physico-chemical properties of the crystal, for example, melting temperature, solubility, stability, etc. can be concluded about. However, such qualitative analysis can be replaced by quantitative analyzes based on quantum-chemical approaches. It is based on the calculation of a surface with the same electron charge density, called the Hirshfeld surface. As a result, it becomes possible to quantify the interaction between two or more molecules.*

Key words: *Hirshfeld surface, intermolecular interaction, hydrogen bonds, solvent system*

Annotatsiya. *Ushbu maqolada [Cu(p-GBK)₂(MEA)₂] kompleksi uchun molekulalarning kristall joylashuvi tahlil qilindi. Ushbu tahlil molekulalararo o'zaro ta'sirlar natijasida qanday supramolekulyar tuzilmalar (2 yoki 3 o'lchovli karkas) hosil bo'lishini aniqlash uchun zarur, chunki u kristalning fizik-kimyoviy xususiyatlariga bog'liq, masalan, erish harorati, eruvchanligi, barqarorligi va boshqalar haqida xulosa qilish mumkin. Biroq bunday sifat tahlili kvant-kimyoviy yondashuvlarga asoslangan miqdoriy tahlillar bilan almashtirilishi mumkin. U Xirshfeld yuzasi deb ataladigan elektron zaryad zichligi bir xil bo'lgan sirtni hisoblashga asoslangan. Natijada, ikki yoki undan ortiq molekulalar orasidagi o'zaro ta'sirni miqdoriy aniqlash mumkin bo'ladi.*

Kalit soʻzlar: *Xirshfeld yuzasi, molekulalararo oʻzaro taʼsir, vodorod bogʻlari, erituvchi sistema*

Аннотация. *В данной статье проанализировано кристаллическое расположение молекула комплекс [Cu(n-ГБК)₂(МЭА)₂]. Этот анализ необходим для определения того, какие супрамолекулярные структуры (2- или 3-мерный каркас) образуются в результате межмолекулярных взаимодействий, поскольку это зависит от физико-химических свойств кристалла, например, температуры плавления, растворимости, стабильность и т.д. можно сделать вывод. Однако такой качественный анализ может быть заменен количественным анализом, основанным на квантово-химических подходах. Он основан на расчете поверхности с одинаковой плотностью заряда электронов, называемой поверхностью Хиршфельда. В результате становится возможным количественно оценить взаимодействие между двумя или более молекулами.*

Ключевые слова: *поверхность Хиршфельда, межмолекулярное взаимодействие, водородные связи, система растворителей.*

Introduction.

Hirshfeld surface analysis is necessary to determine what kind of supramolecular structures (2- or 3-dimensional framework) are formed as a result of intermolecular interactions, because depending on it the physico-chemical properties of the crystal, for example, melting temperature, solubility, stability, etc. can be concluded. However, such qualitative analysis may be replaced by quantitative analyzes based on quantum-chemical approaches. It is based on the calculation of a surface with the same electron charge density, called the Hirshfeld surface. As a result, it becomes possible to quantify the interaction between two or more molecules. With the help of the so-called “fingerprint” patterns, it is possible to estimate the percentage of the total interaction of certain types of interactions, for example, intermolecular N···O connections [1; p. 1008]. In this section, this possibility is analyzed on the example of 2 complexes with a large percentage of intermolecular hydrogen bonds. We have also provided images with highlighted areas to make the analysis results clearer. The isolated regions were matched with the data by defining which parts of the molecule they correspond to.

2. Results and discussion

2.2 Hirshfeld surface analysis of the [Cu(PHBA)₂(MEA)₂] complex

The internal molecular interactions in the crystal structure can be deeply in detail by Hirshfeld surface-to-surface investigations. Plots of the molecular Hirshfeld surface on d_{norm} and distorted fingerprints of [Cu(PHBA)₂(MEA)₂] generated using standard surface dimensions are presented (see Fig. 3 a) and b).

The dnorm surface was mapped in the range -0.7033 a.u.–1.3192 a.u. for O3-H3•••O4) and intermolecular hydrogen bonding interactions are given as bright red spots (see Fig. 1, (a)).

According to published papers worldwide, H•••H and O•••H/H•••O intermolecular interactions in complex compounds are most abundant in the crystal cell. In the complex in Figure 1. almost 54.1% of the molecular surface is due to H•••H bonds formed as a result of the interaction of hydrogens of the methylene and benzene rings. It can be seen that van der Waals forces have an important effect on stabilizing the arrangement in the crystal structure.

Figure 1. Map of Hirshfeld surfaces for dnorm (a) and relative contributions of intramolecular interactions (b)

The contribution of O•••H/ H•••O interactions (mainly H bonds) is 26.5% and is reflected in the fingerprint map as arrow-shape. Other interactions have lower Hirshfeld fields with amounts of C•••H/H•••C (11.8%), C•••C (4.8%) and S•••O/O•••C (2.7%) .

C•••H/H•••C effects show characteristic "wings" in the fingerprint plots, which are due to weak C-H••• π interactions. The shape index and curvedness are -0.996–0.994 a.u and -3.667 -0.224 a.u to describe the intermolecular interactions in more detail (see Figure 1 (a) and (b)).

The Hirshfeld surface is plotted against the electrostatic potential energy set at the B3LYP/STO-3G level based on Hartree-Fock theory in the range 0.0500-0.0500 a.u. Hydrogen bond donors and acceptors are shown as blue and red regions around atoms corresponding to positive and negative potentials, respectively (c). The red triangles represented by concave regions in the figure index indicate p-effects, while the blue triangles represented by convex regions indicate the ring atoms of the molecule within the surface (see Fig. 2, (a)).

The red triangles in the figure shown through the concave regions indicate π - attraction. The red regions inside the surface occupy 11.3% of the C-H••• π area in terms of the 2D surface area. C•••C bonds are located between C1-C6 phenyl rings

with a distance of 3.701(2) Å between the ring centers as a result of $\pi \cdots \pi$ interactions. The corresponding fingerprint plots clearly show a blue area with a diagonal of about 1.9 Å, which is characteristic of $\pi \cdots \pi$ interactions.

Figure 2. Hirshfeld surfaces with shape index (a), curvedness (b) and three-dimensionality (c)

Surface curvedness indicate electron density around molecular interactions (see Figure 2(b)). Flat areas of the surface correspond to low values of curvedness, while areas of sharp curvedness correspond to high values of curvedness and usually tend to reflect on the surface, indicating interactions between neighboring molecules. The large flat region outlined in blue represents the $\pi \cdots \pi$ interaction. The curvedness of this combination indicates the power of interaction $\pi \cdots \pi$ [5, p. 4230].

Figure 2-c shows the calculated electrostatic potential of the molecule forming the Hirshfeld surface of the analyzed complex (see Figure 2, (c)). The negative potential (acceptor) is shown as a red surface area around the eight atoms (O1-O4 and O1a-O4a), and the blue surface area representing the positive potential (donor) is mapped near the hydrogen atoms.

3. Conclusion

The concave portions in the depicted picture of $[\text{Cu}(\text{p-HBA})_2(\text{MEA})_2]$ are denoted by red triangles, which signify the occurrence of π - π -attraction. The red patches located within the surface constitute approximately 11.3% of the C-H \cdots π area, as measured in terms of the two-dimensional surface area. The C \cdots C bonds are situated between the C1-C6 phenyl rings, with a measured distance of 3.701(2) Å between the centres of the rings. This distance is attributed to the presence of $\pi \cdots \pi$ interactions. The fingerprint plots exhibit a distinct blue region with a diagonal length of approximately 1.9 Å, indicative of $\pi \cdots \pi$ interactions.

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